

Tailoring the Design of Web Questionnaires to the Completion Process in Business Surveys: About Audit trails, Eye-tracking and other methods

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Abstract

Data collection using electronic or web questionnaires brings new possibilities to study data quality issues. One approach is audit trails, a kind of paradata: event log data showing when and how respondents complete a questionnaire. Audit trails are a rich source of data, and can be used to derive various indicators of questionnaire completion, e.g.:

- Completion indicators: completion time, numbers of sessions
- Navigation behaviour: the use of function keys (Forward, Backward, Print);
- Profiles of questionnaire completion;
- Completion course: When do respondents work on the questionnaire?

These indicators can be used to improve the questionnaire and the survey communication strategy, by tailoring these to the completion process of the respondent. Research showing the utility of audit trails will be presented, using the Dutch Annual Structural Business Survey as example.

Next to audit trails, eye-tracking (as used by e.g. Destatis in Germany) is a new method to study the completion process. Examples of the use of eye-tracking, based on experiences in Germany, will be discussed. Used in combination with other qualitative and quantitative methods (pre-testing, debriefing, response and data-editing analysis), we have a good toolkit for evaluating and improving the survey design.

KeyWords: Paradata, Audit trails, Eye-tracking, Electronic/Web questionnaire, Pre-test and Evaluation methods, questionnaire completion behaviour

1. Introduction: stages in questionnaire design

Traditionally, National Statistical Institutes (NSIs) rely on surveys using questionnaires for the production of statistics. Important quality issues with regard to surveys are to obtain complete and unbiased data in time. Nowadays, many NSIs are developing mixed-mode designs both for social and business surveys, in which internet questionnaires (CAWI) are developed next to traditional modes like paper, CAPI and CATI (Snijkers, 2009; Snijkers, Göttgens, Hermans, 2011). Drivers for implementing web surveys are: cost-efficiency reasons, improving data quality, and response burden reduction.

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This has consequences for a number of aspects of the production of Statistics, like production costs, operations, data quality and response burden. To make sure that the goals are reached, the survey needs to be designed and implemented carefully, which includes: the sample design, the questionnaire design, the survey communication strategy, data capture, coding and cleaning methodology, and operational issues. To see if the goals are met, the survey needs to be developed taking known information about the completion process into account, tested prior to the fieldwork, monitored during the fieldwork, and evaluated afterwards.

In this paper we will focus on the design of a questionnaire, a web questionnaire in particular to be used in a mixed-mode survey. In this process three stages can be identified: the development stage, the pre-field testing stage, and the fieldwork stage (Willimack, 2013). In the questionnaire development stage, the questionnaire is developed in the course of two steps: conceptualization and operationalisation (Snijkers & Willimack, 2011). In the conceptualisation step the translation from concepts to indicators or attributes is made. The starting point is to think carefully about the concepts that are to be studied (Willeboordse, 1998; Brancato et al., 2006). The researcher first decides what concepts are of interest, and secondly, how to define those concepts. For a concept of interest one or more indicators are defined which combined measure this concept. Concepts can be simple, existing of only one indicator. In that case we have a one-dimensional concept, e.g. 'gender'. In economic research, however, most concepts are multi-dimensional, indicating that a concept is composed out of more indicators.

Indicators are the link between the theoretical and empirical world. In the case of a survey, questions in a questionnaire are specified to measure these indicators. Questions are the operationalisation of these indicators; they are the operational definitions (Segers, 1977; De Groot, 1994) according to which the indicators are measured. This includes the wording of a question, answering options, and instructions. A question can be based on a single indicator, resulting in a one-dimensional question; it can also be based on a combination of indicators, resulting in a multi-dimensional question.

The next step is the design of the questionnaire, i.e. the operationalisation or construction of the measuring instrument. It involves: (re)writing the questions, (re)defining answering options, (re)writing instructions, composing blocks of questions that are related, putting the blocks and questions in order (e.g., according to theme), navigation, edit checks, as well as the visual design. Aspects of the questionnaire design may vary depending on the data collection mode. Additionally, questionnaires may be tailored to subgroups. (See Haraldsen, 2013a, for a detailed discussion on business survey questionnaire design; see also Couper, 2008, with regard to web surveys.)

Once the questionnaire constructed, it is pre-tested. This includes the pre-testing of the questionnaire design, the usability of the questionnaire, as well as the testing of the operational process. Finally, in the third stage, the questionnaire and the data collection process are monitored and evaluated during and after the fieldwork. The results of each stage are input for the next. The results of the final stage (evaluation of the questionnaire in the field) provide input for improvement of the questionnaire for a next cycle. As such these stages and methods relate to the Deming or PDCA-cycle (Plan-Do-Check-Act), which is a key element of quality management (Snijkers, Haraldsen & Jones, 2013).

In each of these three stages various methods can be used. These methods will be discussed in the next section. In the remainder of this paper we will focus on two methods: eye tracking (in section 3) and audit trails (in section 4). We will argue that these methods are a relevant supplement in our toolkit of questionnaire test and evaluation methods. We will illustrate this with a number of examples from our experience. Section 5 concludes this paper with a general discussion on these methods.

2. Questionnaire Development, Testing and Evaluation Methods

2.1 An overview of methods

In the previous section we identified three stages in the process of designing a questionnaire: development, pre-testing and evaluation. For each of these stages, we have a number of methods in our toolkit. An overview of these methods is presented in figure 1: a tree structure shows the methods that can be used depending on the stage and the goals. Some of the methods that are listed can be used in various stages, like focus groups. This method can be used in all three stages. For a detailed discussion on these methods we refer to Willimack (2013), and Snijkers & Haraldsen (2013) (see also Willimack et al., 2004; Snijkers, 2002; Willis, 2005; Brancato et al., 2006). In this paper we will focus on eye-tracking and audit trails.

Figure 1: An overview of methods

At the first level we identify the three stages of questionnaire design: development, testing and evaluation. For each stage goals are listed. This comes down to asking: “What kind of information do I need in order to design a valid and respondent-friendly questionnaire that fits smoothly in the existing production process?” In general, these goals relate to:

- data quality (like non-sampling errors related to the questionnaire: non-response errors, measurement errors, and processing errors, but also relevance and timeliness (Haraldsen, 2013b),
- response burden (like mismatch issues in response categories, mismatch issues in definitions, need of help, calculations, lay-out and usability issues (Haraldsen, Jones, Giesen & Zhang, 2013) , and
- operational issues (like cost-efficient data collection processes).

These goals can be linked to the various parties involved in a survey: the stakeholder or data user, the respondent, and the survey organisation.

At the next level, these goals are specified in more detail if needed. E.g. is a pre-test focussed at the cognitive process (to study the Question-Answer process) or technical aspects (to test if the questionnaire is programmed correctly). And at the final level, the methods are listed.

2.2 Studying Web Questionnaire Design

The introduction of web questionnaires brings new possibilities to study questionnaire design issues. And what is more, this mode even makes it essential and indispensable to test and evaluate the questionnaire with use of new technologies in the pre-field and field stage.

Since the mid 1980's questionnaires have been pre-tested using cognitive interviewing methods. Testing questionnaires is aimed at improving the validity of the questionnaire, and thus reducing measurement and non-response errors in surveys. These methods study the completion process:

- How do respondent interpret a question? How do they get to their answer?
- How do they interpret the tasks they have to carry out?

These testing methods are aimed at studying the cognitive processes, i.e. comprehension of the questions and the completion tasks (see e.g. Tourangeau, Rips & Rasinksi, 2000; Snijkers, 2002; Willis, 2005).

With the use of self-administered web questionnaires another aspect is introduced to the completion process: the usability of questionnaires. The user interface, visual design and navigation in web questionnaires are also sources of error that may lead to measurement and non-response errors. Here we are dealing with questions like:

- How do respondents handle the questionnaire?
- What is the usability of the (visual) design?

When testing a questionnaire, these error sources also need to be studied.

The traditional testing methods are applied in the pre-field stage, to pre-test a questionnaire prior to using it in the field, and in the post-field stage to evaluate the questionnaire. These methods are qualitative in nature. On average, between 10 and 15 respondents are interviewed in a test study, revealing an overview of errors in the questionnaire design. The respondents are selected in such a way that they represent the target population. But because of this small number it is hard to generalise the findings to the population at large.

Also these methods are indirect, in the sense that the completion process is studied indirectly in a laboratory situation or retrospectively. Furthermore, when used concurrently, these methods disturb the completion process: an interviewer conducts cognitive interviews using e.g. think-aloud probes.

Pre-testing methods have been proven to be of great value in the questionnaire design process to ensure the development of a valid questionnaire. In methodological handbooks they are recommended. The American Statistical Association (Schueren, 2004, p. 44) e.g. recommends to "pretest, pretest, and then pretest some more." Also the European Statistics Code of Practice (Eurostat, 2011: principle 8), states that questionnaires need to be "systematically tested prior to the data collection." Bradburn, Sudman and Wansink (2004, p. 314) even advice to drop the survey all together "if you do not have the resources to pilot test".

These methods, however, have also some drawbacks and have met some criticism (Snijkers 2002). By using these methods it is hard to study the completion process in real time, and to get quantitative data. To overcome these issues, new test and evaluation methods using new technologies can be applied. In this paper we will discuss two new methods: eye-tracking, and audit trails (and paradata in general), that supplement traditional pre-testing methods.

2.2.1 Eye-tracking

Eye-tracking is a method to study the completion of questionnaires by following the eye movement of respondents. It offers a lab method to study the completion of a questionnaire without interference of an interviewer. A set-up of eye-tracking is shown in figure 2. The two cameras at the bottom of the computer screen are fixed at the eyes of the respondent. These cameras register the eye-movements.

Figure 2. Set-up of an eye-tracker

Eye-tracking collects data with regard to:

- What respondents look at on the screen, and in what sequence?
- Eye-fixations, which is the when an eye is fixed at a specific point on the screen. The number and length of eye-fixations may be an indication for the efforts needed to comprehend a questionnaire.

The German Federal Statistical Office has developed a three-stage approach to use eye-tracking. In a lab setting, firstly, eye movements and facial expressions (in real-time) are recorded using the eye-tracker and observed by an observer, while respondents complete the questionnaire. Secondly, a cognitive interview is conducted, in which the video of the eye movements is shown to the respondent. By using the methods of retrospective thinking aloud and probing, reasons for wrong, incomplete or missing answers are investigated. In a third step, the eye tracking data (fixation length, number of fixations etc.) are analysed and interpreted. As such, information from these three stages is combined (“triangulation”), thus providing higher data quality in terms of more objective test results and a richer overall picture.

Eye-tracking can be a very useful method in pre-testing questionnaires, because it provides insights into the unconscious behaviour of respondents. This behaviour also has

a strong influence on the completion process and consequently determines data quality. For example, the order in which respondents look at a questionnaire screen and where they look, can hardly be described in words, as they don't think actively about it.

A more detailed discussion on eye-tracking is provided by Galesic and Yan (2011; see also Willimack, 2013). In section 3, the benefit of eye-tracking in questionnaire testing will be illustrated with examples from pre-tests conducted by Destatis (Tries, 2011).

2.2.2 Audit trails and paradata

Audit trails are a way to study the completion of web questionnaires in the field. Audit trails are event-log data showing when and how respondents work on a questionnaire. They are a kind of paradata, i.e. process data on the client side (in contrast to paradata on the production process of surveys; see e.g. Heerwegh, 2011; Couper & Lyberg, 2005). With the use of computers, paradata on all computerised survey processes can be collected, in order to monitor the processes in real time in responsive survey designs (Snijkers & Haraldsen, 2013; Kreuter, Couper & Lyberg, 2010; Groves & Heeringa, 2006).

Statistics Netherlands has analysed audit trails for business surveys, revealing a lot of information on the actual completion process. In 2004-2005 the Annual Dutch Structural Business was redesigned to be a web survey (in a mixed-mode design): a downloadable electronic questionnaire was developed in Blaise (see Snijkers, Onat & Vis, 2007, for a detailed description of the development process). This questionnaire was used in the field in 2007; it also collected audit trails: for 42,000 businesses that used the electronic questionnaire, 11.5 million records of audit trail data have been collected (see figure 3).

	id	date	time	action	field	value
1	12345	22-MAY-2007	10:43:17	0	0	
2	12345	22-MAY-2007	10:43:58	1	40	
3	12345	22-MAY-2007	10:44:19	2	40	01-04-2005
4	12345	22-MAY-2007	10:44:19	14	40	
5	12345	22-MAY-2007	10:44:29	14	27	
6	12345	22-MAY-2007	10:44:48	14	21	
7	12345	22-MAY-2007	10:44:51	1	48	
8	12345	22-MAY-2007	10:45:15	3	48	
9	12345	22-MAY-2007	10:50:20	8	48	
10	12345	22-MAY-2007	10:51:05	10	48	
11	12345	22-MAY-2007	10:51:05	99	0	
12	12345	20-JUN-2007	8:52:28	0	0	
13	12345	20-JUN-2007	8:53:09	8	15	
14	12345	20-JUN-2007	8:54:50	13	15	
15	12345	20-JUN-2007	8:54:53	11	15	
16	12345	20-JUN-2007	8:55:02	9	15	
17	12345	20-JUN-2007	9:35:58	99	0	
18	12345	29-JUN-2007	15:10:38	0	0	

Figure 3. A part of a file showing audit trail data

From these data various measures of questionnaire completion have been derived, like:

- Completion indicators like completion time or number of sessions;
- Navigation behaviour, like the use of function buttons (e.g., Forward, Backward, Print);
- Profiles of questionnaire completion;
- Completion course: when do respondents work on the questionnaire?

In addition, these data can be used to identify:

- Questions for which the answers have been changed frequently,
- Locations in the questionnaire where respondents did have a break, or even stopped completing.

These measures indicate where respondents may have had difficulties in completing the questionnaire. In section 4 the vast possibilities of audit trails will be illustrated with examples from this case study conducted by Statistics Netherlands (Snijkers & Morren, 2010; Chan, Morren & Snijkers, 2011).

3. Eye-tracking

In this section we will discuss three examples coming from usability studies conducted by Destatis (Tries, 2011) that will illustrate the usefulness of eye-tracking as a questionnaire testing method. These examples show where respondents looked on the screen, with regard to the perception and understanding of navigation instructions, completion instructions and error messages. The first example, as shown figure 4, has to do with instructions.

Figure 4. Eye-tracking and instructions

In figure 4 we see two screens with fixations of two respondents. The longer a respondent was fixed at one spot, the larger the red circles. We can also see the order of fixations, so the sequence of details respondents looked at. The text on the screen explains the structure of the questionnaire and how to navigate to the respondent: the questionnaire is composed of a number of blocks which are shown as tabs at the top of the screen. By clicking on the tabs one moves from one block to next, or moves backward. Also the instructions tell the respondent how to save and submit the data. These instructions refer to two of the three tabs at the right side of the screen. Respondents are supposed to read these instructions well before they start completing the questionnaire.

The fixations of Respondent 1, show that this respondent reads the instructions quite intensively (many fixations, very close together). Respondent 2, the right side of figure 4, reads the instructions more superficially, but also checks the tabs, as they are described in the text.

During the cognitive interview Respondent 1 told the interviewer that he/she read and understood the instructions. Still, it showed that during the completion of the questionnaire this respondent didn't know how to send the data. The question now is what caused this usability problem. If we would only have conducted cognitive interviews, the information we had collected about the completion process would tell us that the instructions had been read and comprehended; and our question could not be answered. The eye-tracking data however provided the answer: Respondent 1 did read the instructions but did relate the text to the tabs. As a consequence a better visual connection between the text and the tabs is needed.

In a second example, as shown in figure 5, instructions are printed in bold face to highlight important information with regard to the completion of this questionnaire, like the day of reference (22 November 2010).

Figure 5. Eye-tracking and bold-faced information.

During the cognitive interviews, respondents told the interviewer that they had read the instructions completely. The profile of fixations of Respondent 1, however, shows otherwise: he/she only read the instructions superficially, he/she skimmed the text, and did not read the bolded words! Respondent 2 read the instructions quite thoroughly, as the fixations show, but also gave no special attention to the bolded words. A more detailed analysis of these eye-tracking data for all respondents indicated that there was no higher fixation rate or mean fixation duration on bolded words, compared to other words. As a consequence it can be concluded that using bold faced text to attract attention doesn't always work, at least not in this questionnaire (maybe because bold faced text is used too much).

Eye-tracking also proved to be helpful in identifying the reasons why error messages were misunderstood and not follow-up. This is the third example to illustrate the usefulness of eye-tracking in combination with cognitive interviewing.

In this particular questionnaire, error messages appear on the screen after respondents have clicked on <Send>. In the worst case they got a long list of error messages, placed in a window on top of the questionnaire, saying e.g.:

Questionnaire contains errors: ✖

You have not completed the questions for this dwelling:

- Dwelling question [Dwelling 1] | Question 1
- Question W1: Inhabitant 1

You have not listed any possessions for this dwelling, even though you have entered G5, meaning that the possessions are in community of property:

- Dwelling question [Dwelling 1] Questions
W2-W4 Question W2: Possession of dwelling

The observations during the completion of the questionnaire showed that respondents ignored the error messages, and closed this window immediately after showing up. Hard error checks resulted in anger and frustration. The cognitive interviews identified the following reasons for this behaviour:

- The error messages are written in green, which is not easy to read,

- The content of the instructions is not clear, and respondents didn't know what these messages meant,
- Respondents didn't understand that they had to click on a link to be directed to the wrong answer.

Eye-tracking revealed what actually happened: respondents only looked at the header of the list of error checks, and almost completely ignored the rest. Based on the combination of results, this indicates that for error messages to work, they should be shown at the end of each screen, so respondents can make the connections between the error message and the questions they have just answered; and the instructions should be in plain, understandable text.

4. Audit trails

As said above an electronic version of the SBS questionnaire has been developed by Statistics Netherlands. This Questionnaire is shown in figure 6 (see Snijkers, Onat & Vis, 2007). With this questionnaire audit trails as shown in figure 3 have been collected. On the basis of these audit trails several measures on how the SBS is filled in and utilised are calculated. We make a distinction between information regarding completion of and navigation in the electronic questionnaire. *Completion* information refers to how the questionnaire (program) is used, and involves measures such as completion time, number of sessions, session duration, etc. This also refers to the completion course. *Navigation* information describes how the process of filling in the questions has proceeded, and includes use of the help function, number of attempts to send the questionnaire, when the questionnaire has been printed, and browsing behaviour. Below we will discuss completion and navigation indicators as well as the completion course.

The screenshot shows a web-based questionnaire interface. The main section is titled 'Werkzame personen' and includes the following fields and labels:

- Werknemers op de eigen loonlijst per 30 september**
 - Totaal aantal
 - Omgerekend in voltijdequivalenten (VTE, op één decimaal nauwkeurig)
- Overige werkzame personen per 30 september**
 - Medewerkende eigenaren en gezinsleden
 - Uitzendkrachten / gedetacheerd personeel (van uitzendbedrijven)
 - Overig ingeleend personeel (van andere bedrijven)
- Subtotaal aantal werknemers en overige werkzame personen**
- Totaal aantal personen werkzaam in uw bedrijf**
- Totaal aantal personen werkzaam in uw bedrijf omgerekend in voltijdequivalenten (VTE, op één decimaal nauwkeurig)**

At the bottom right of the form area, there is a yellow button labeled 'Akkoord +'. The taskbar at the bottom contains icons for 'Verzenden', 'Afdrukken', 'Opslaan', 'Stoppen', 'Calculator', 'Rekenveld', and 'Informatie'.

Figure 6. Screen shot of the electronic SBS questionnaire

4.1 Completion and navigation information

Both completion and navigation information can be used to obtain general information about the effort it takes respondents to complete a questionnaire. Questions with regard

to the completion and navigation behaviour that can be answered with this information relate to what respondents do step-by-step, and include:

- Do respondents complete the questionnaire in one session, or in several sessions?
- How long does it take to complete a questionnaire as a whole?
- How do respondents navigate through the questionnaire?
- Do respondents use the print function? How often and at what moments in the completion process do they print the questionnaire?
- Do respondents first browse through the questionnaire before they start filling it in (to get an overview of the questionnaire), or do they start filling it in right away question-by-question?

Table 1 shows some examples of completion measures. These measures can be provided at the session level and at the questionnaire level. Table 2 shows some of the measures of how respondents navigate through the questionnaire. This gives a general impression of how respondents use the questionnaire.

Table 1. Completion measures

Completion (n=41,274 respondents)	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Session (n=67,479)				
• Number of actions	2	2209	165	156
• Duration of session	0:00:01	10:50:15	0:41:20	0:59:27
Questionnaire (n=41,274)				
• Number of actions	42	2209	270	210
• Number of sessions	1	35	1.6	1.4
• Completion time	0:00:20	59:05:57	1:07:34	1:58:11
• Start-finish lag (days)	1	428	7.9	23.3

Table 2. Navigation measures

Navigation (n=41,274 respondents)	Used by % of respondents	Mean if used	SD	Min-Max
Start	100	1.6	1.4	1 – 32
Help	45	5.3	6.2	1 – 82
Send	100	1.3	0.7	1 – 13
Print	43	1.7	1.3	1 – 27
Save	29	2.6	4.2	1 – 104
Calculator	5	1.9	2.4	1 – 38
Information	13	1.4	1.5	1 – 97
Forward	46	13.5	20.5	1 – 346
Backward	65	14.8	19.8	1 – 325
Confirmation	100	33.1	18.6	12 – 316

In addition to these measures, a number of *completion profiles* were identified. These profiles are examples of individual ways of completing the questionnaire. We identified the conscientious (Figure 7), the quick-and-dirty (Figure 8), and the ‘printer’ respondent (Figure 9).

These figures show what respondents have done step-by-step. In order to get these graphs we numbered the questions from 1 to over 300, which is the y-axis. The unit of the x-axis is the action number, but shown is the time (which is a non-linear scale). As a result, Figure 7 shows e.g. a respondent going through the questionnaire from the first to

Figure 7. The conscientious respondent

Figure 8. The 'quick-and-dirty' respondent

Figure 9. The 'printer' respondent

the final question, then going back in the questionnaire and going over the final part again for four times. Then after about 2 hours, the program is stopped. In this first session the questionnaire is saved and printed three times (but not always at the same moments), as show the lines at the top of this graph. On the same day a second session is started in which the respondent goes back and forth in the questionnaire again. This session takes about 50 minutes. At the end of this session the questionnaire is sent. Then a few more sessions are started and the questionnaire is sent some more times. This conscientious respondent completed the questionnaire in about 3 hours in a number of sessions on one day. Figure 8 shows the 'quick-and-dirty' respondent who completed the questionnaire in just over 4 minutes and sending it several times. The respondent in Figure 9 completed the questionnaire in almost 18 minutes, first by going over the questionnaire quickly, then printing it, stopping the program, and completing the questionnaire in a second session on another day in about 15 minutes. From this profile we assume that the questionnaire is completed on paper before entering the data.

4.2 Response completion course

Next to the completion and navigation behaviour we were interested in when respondents actually worked on the questionnaire. We would like to know whether reminders are effective in motivating respondents to fill in the questionnaire and to respond to the survey. Response analysis of the SBS-2006 (Morren 2009; Morren, Snijkers & Kempkers 2009) revealed that about 2/3rd of the initial sample (63,644 units) needed to be reminded for a first time (44,917 units), about half needed a second reminder (30,102 units), and about a quarter of the initial sample is reminded three times (17,516 units). The average response time for business that completed the electronic questionnaire is 2.8 months (for all businesses, including the paper questionnaire, it is 3.5 months). In addition we would like to know what happened in these months: what did respondents do? Why does it take so long to get the response back?

The contact strategy for the SBS includes three reminders. The questionnaire was dispatched in April and May 2007 in 11 clusters. After 9-13 weeks a first reminder was sent out, followed by a second reminder after 2-6 weeks and a subsequent third reminder 3-13 weeks later. This means that businesses in different clusters complete the questionnaire on different moments in time.

To compare the response courses for all clusters, all clusters have been transformed to a single starting point '0', resulting in the black line in Figure 10. We see a peak immediately after dispatching the questionnaire, then the response drops. A second peak is associated with the first and second reminders.

The research question with regard to the use of audit trails is related to the response course and the contact strategy: When do respondents actually complete the questionnaire? Or, in other words: Do businesses respond because of a reminder even when the data are available at an earlier stage, or do they do so independent of reminders. In this process, three actions are relevant:

- Opening the questionnaire for the first time (incidence);
- Filling-in the questionnaire (prevalence); and
- Sending the data (i.e. response).

Figure 10. Response course, completion incidence and prevalence, after questionnaire dispatch

Figure 10 shows that incidence and prevalence followed the response pattern. Combined with the fact that the average completion duration is 7.9 days (as shown in table 1: start-finish lag), this lead to the hypothesis that respondents completed the questionnaire in a short period of time immediately after opening the questionnaire for the first time. An analysis with regard to the duration of the completion showed that this is indeed the case. We found a very skewed distribution (Figure 11; Chan et al., 2011): 75.8% of the respondents started working with the questionnaire, completing it and sending the data in 1 day, 85% of the respondents completed this process in 7 days (one week). Taking the fact in mind that the average response time is 2.8 months, we came to believe that in the mean time nothing happened: no completion activities what so ever, as is shown in figure 12.

Figure 11. Completion duration

Figure 12. Timeline of completion

To conclude, this analysis showed that most businesses completed the questionnaire within a short period of time, within a small number of sessions, and immediately after they first started working on it. These data don't show what made them work on the questionnaire; that would require a post-field study into the completion process. Pre-test studies on this process, however, give some information. Very likely it is a combination of two factors: the contact strategy stimulates businesses to comply with the survey; but they probably do not start working on the questionnaire until their conditions are met, i.e. when the data and recourses are available to complete the questionnaire. As a consequence it seems worthwhile to tailor the communication strategy to the response process in businesses. Sending questionnaires at an earlier moment in time, in order to get response back sooner, does not seem an effective strategy.

5. Conclusion:

Combining audit trails, eye-tracking and traditional pre-testing

Eye-tracking offers a way to study the completion process in small scale without interviewer interference of the completion process. This method also offers a way to study the usability of self-administered web questionnaires. Through the addition of a cognitive interview, further information about the reasons for completion behaviour can be gathered.

Audit trails are quantitative data offering insights in the actual completion behaviour of respondents. But, audit trails only show what respondents actually did; these data don't show why this behaviour occurred. As such audit trails are a means to generate hypotheses about the questionnaire and the completion process. While eye-tracking and cognitive pre-testing methods can be used to investigate these hypotheses.

By combining these methods a new toolkit for survey methodologists is developed to evaluate the completion process. By applying these methods the survey design, i.e. the questionnaire and the survey communication strategy, can be improved by tailoring these survey components to the completion process of the respondent.

Although these methods supplement traditional pre-testing and result in valuable information about the completion process, the application of these methods needs to be carefully planned, for a number of reasons:

- Both eye-tracking and audit trails generate lots of data. Before using these methods the methodologist needs to think about the research questions, and the ways these data need to be analysed. This is a time-consuming process.
- Think carefully about the interpretation of the findings: what do they indicate? As we seen above these methods show what is happening, not why it is happening. To find out about the 'why', these methods can be used in combination with cognitive interviewing methods, like in the three-stage approach as carried out by Destatis (as described in section 2.2.1).
- The data collected with these methods are data like any data. This means that we to deal with all kinds of errors in the data. For eye-tracking e.g., the laboratory setting can influence the behaviour of the respondents. With regard to the audit trails, the time measured may not be accurate, when the questionnaire is open while the respondent is not working on it (e.g. having lunch; overreporting) or he is working on it while the questionnaire is closed (e.g. checking business records; underreporting). Also the computer clock may not be synchronised with the actual time.
- How to deal with logistics? For business respondents it is hard to invite them to come to the laboratory, so we have to go them. This means that we have to bring the eye-tracker to the field (which requires a mobile system).
- Ethical issues. And finally we have to think about ethical issues and informed consent: It is allowed to collect all these data from respondents, even if it is for research purposes.

To conclude, an efficient way of applying eye-tracking and audit trails seems to be:

- Use these methods to get general insights in the completion process, in combination with other methods. These insights can be used to develop standards in questionnaire design.
- For the testing of individual questionnaires (which design is based on these insights) traditional pre-testing and debriefing methods seems more efficient.

9. References

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